

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/MsAKHILDEV N bearing USN 6SU19CC001has completed his/her Internship at Manipal Hospital Hebbal in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AMRUTHA K MANOJ bearing USN 6SU19CC002 has completed his/her Internship at Manipal Hospital Hebbal in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/MsANUROOP K DAS bearing USN 6SU19CC003has completed his/her Internship at Manipal Hospital Hebbal in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms FABINA. P V bearing USN 6SU19CC004 has completed his/her Internship at Manipal Hospital Hebbal in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms FATHIMATH SANA AHAMMAD bearing USN 6SU19CC005 has completed his/her Internship at Manipal Hospital Hebbal in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsJUMANATH V bearing USN 6SU19CC006has completed his/her Internship at Manipal Hospital Hebbal in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsSANCHITHA B bearing USN 6SU19CC007 has completed his/her Internship at Manipal Hospital Hebbal in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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